

Development of A Relevant Communicant Catechization Teaching Module in Indonesian Christian Lutheran Church

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Abstract

This research is based on the root of the problem. The main problem is that the Indonesian Lutheran Christian Church has no Catechism Teaching Module. Therefore, catechism teachers in the church experience difficulties in teaching. Students need help to follow the lesson. Previously, what was used was Martin Luther's Catechism. It took material from other sources so that the catechism teaching would convey no uniformity in the subject matter. The research results are as follows. First, the feasibility of the Communicative catechism module based on results from material, design, and language experts was 88.28%. It shows that the module is suitable for users with small group trials, with a score of 83.46%, and large groups, with a score of 84.54%, in the category very worthy. Second, the effectiveness of the Communicant Catechization teaching module is based on a Post-Test score of 80.28, so the Communicant Catechization teaching module is in the suitable category for use. Finally, the research concluded that the product developed was feasible, effective, and useful for use as a Communicant Catechism teaching module.

1. Introduction

One of the GKLI (*Gereja Kristen Luther Indonesia*/ Indonesian Christian Lutheran Church) programs is service to teenagers/youth as future successors of the church. In general, churches should already have a systematic and measurable catechization Communicant Teaching Module (Blåder, 2015). Based on the interviews with GKLI leaders/Bishops, information was obtained that

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there was no communicant catechism teaching module, so students had difficulty following the lesson because they were only guided by Martin Luther's Catechism (Luther, 2020). This is due to the limited number of teaching staff with a religious education background capable of compiling Communicant catechism modules. The implementation of Communicant catechism teaching for youth/adolescents at GKLI is of particular concern to the author in creating teaching modules for Pastors or catechism teachers (Cf. Daud et al., 2021).

2. Materials and Methods

This type of research is Research and Development (R&D) (Cf. Yuliyana et al., 2022; Sabrini et al., 2022). The research method used is mixed (combining quantitative and qualitative). According to Creswell, mixed research combines or collaborates qualitative research and quantitative research (Hara, 1995; Morse, 2008; Keith et al., 2022). Problems in this research are studied by applying quantitative and qualitative methods to analyze or interpret data about the quality of products developed through information, responses, and suggestions for improvement from validators obtained through questionnaires or interviews. This research designs or develops a new product that is effective for use in the GKLI Church after going through a food validation and trial process. The resulting product is a relevant Communicative catechism teaching module at GKLI.

3. Results and Discussions

3.1 Potential and Problem Stage

At this stage, an interview was conducted with the leadership of GKLI, the results of which stated that at GKLI, there was no teaching module for the Communicant catechism which had been prepared systematically due to the lack of human resources who could prepare teaching materials for the Communicant catechism at GKLI, so the book used so far in teaching the Communicant catechism was from Martin Luther's Catechism. Based on the problems and potential that can be developed to support services at GKLI, a Communicant catechism teaching module.

3.2 Data Collection Stages

a. Needs Analysis

The results of interviews with the leadership/Bishop of GKLI and the Pastors stated that relevant Communicant catechism teaching modules are needed so that there is uniformity in the material that will be delivered so that the implementation of Communicant catechism learning will run as expected.

b. Material Assessment

There were conducting material studies by distributing questionnaires to 15 resort pastors who actively carry out Communicant catechisms via the Google Form link. Based on the questionnaire results, the pastors believed that the main source of teaching the Communicant catechism should come from Martin Luther's catechism. So the researcher compiled the Communicant catechism

module material based on Martin Luther's catechism, combined with pictures, attractive writing colors, discussion material, and questions, and equipped with an answer key to make it easier for the Communicant catechism teacher to deliver lessons in each material.

3.3 Product Design

At this stage, the researcher designed the Communicative catechism teaching module. Preparing the framework for the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module was based on Martin Luther's GKLI catechism as a reference in preparing the module. In this stage, the researcher developed teaching materials in a module consisting of 40 discussion topics and meeting time once a week for 90 minutes/meeting. Each learning subject consists of sub-topics related to the learning subject. The learning sub-subjects contain a brief introduction to the discussion of the topic or text that will be discussed. The two discussion materials (Assignments) are the questions discussed in the lesson. Third, LKS (Student Worksheet).

3.4 Test results

Materials Expert

The subject matter experts are 5 Pastors and 1 Evangelist, as qualified users of the Communicant catechism teaching module. Overall, the average percentage of the suitability of the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module is 92.24%. This shows that the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module developed by researchers is very suitable for use.

Design and Language Expert

There are two design and language experts. Overall, the average module percentage was 84.32%. This shows that the Communicative catechism teaching module developed is very suitable for use. Based on the results of the assessment questionnaire data analysis test from material experts, design and language experts regarding the feasibility or product quality of the Communicant Catechism teaching module, it shows that the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module is suitable for use with a percentage of 88.28%.

Design Revision

Revisions to the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module were carried out based on responses, criticism, and suggestions from validators to improve the feasibility of the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module. Researchers revised the module design based on validators' responses, suggestions, and criticism. Once repaired, it is returned to the validator.

3.5 Product Trial

Small group trials

A trial was carried out on the Communicant catechism at GKLI. Evaluation of potential users, as many as ten teenagers. From the Analysis of small group evaluation data carried out, the following results were obtained for the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module product;

Table of Small Group Trial Results

Component	Effectiveness Percentage	Score
Learning Materials/Ingredients	85,63	3,43
Discussion	83,75	3,35
Physical Appearance	81,00	3,24
Average	83,46	3,34

Overall, the average percentage of effectiveness (learning materials, discussions, physical appearance) of the Communicant catechism teaching module was obtained with a score of 3.34 (83.46). This shows that the catechism teaching module developed by researchers is very suitable for use at GCLI. The following is presented in the form of a graphic diagram for evaluation results by users.

Large Group Trials

After the small group trial stage, it was then field tested in large groups. Large group trials were conducted on 25 GCLI City Resort teenagers.

Table of Large Group Trial Results

Component	Effectiveness Percentage	Score
Learning Materials/Ingredients	91,25	3,65
Discussion	93,75	3,75
Physical Appearance	92,2	3,69
Average	92,4	3,69

Overall, the average percentage of effectiveness (learning materials, discussions, physical appearance) of the Communicant catechism teaching module was obtained with a score of 3.69 (92.4). This shows that the module developed by researchers is very suitable for use at GCLI Resort Tarutung City.

3.6 Product Revision

Revisions to the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module were carried out based on responses, criticism, and suggestions from trials aimed at improving the feasibility and effectiveness of the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module product. Based on product trials, there were no significant suggestions or criticisms for revising the design of the Communicant Catechism Teaching Module.

3.7 Implementation Trial

At the last meeting, another evaluation was carried out to find out whether there was an increase in youth knowledge at the GCLI church. To determine the module's effectiveness, it is carried out through pre-test and post-test evaluation; then, Analysis is carried out using the t-test.

4. Conclusion

Based on this research and development results, we produced a Relevant Communicant Catechism Teaching Module product in the Indonesian Luther Christian Church. Bishop of GKLI is expected to recommend this Communicant catechism teaching module as a reference book for Communicant learning because, based on research results, this teaching module is suitable for use.

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